

Willingness to Pay for the Protection and Conservation of Forest Ecosystems in the Abra River Basin, Philippines

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Abstract:

The forest ecosystems of the Abra River basin, Philippines, provide various ecosystem goods and services that are important to the wellbeing of its residents. This study used the Contingent Valuation Method (CVM) to estimate the willingness to pay (WTP) of local residents for the protection and conservation of forest ecosystems within the basin. A total of 368 households were involved in the survey. The result showed that 78.26% of the respondents were willing to pay for forest protection and conservation activities. The estimated mean WTP (MWTP) using binary logistic regression is PhP 5.13/month/household. The MWTP was significantly

influenced by marital status and bid amount. Further, the respondents showed awareness of the various goods and services provided by forest ecosystems, especially provisioning services.

Keywords: forest ecosystem services, contingent valuation method, willingness to pay, Philippines.

Introduction

Forest ecosystem services (FES) are benefits offered by forests essential for human well-being (Millennium Ecosystem Assessment (MEA), 2005; Aznar-Sanchez et al., 2018; Rocés-Díaz et al., 2018; Jo et al., 2021). Forest ecosystem services are broadly classified into four types: (1) provisioning, which includes the production of timber, food, and water; (2) regulating, which includes the control of climate, flood, and disease; (3) supporting, which includes nutrient cycles and crop pollination; and (4) cultural, which includes spiritual and recreational benefits. Quantifying and valuing forest ecosystem services has received a lot of attention

(Xie et al., 2010). Economic valuation of forest ecosystem services is critical for developing and implementing effective sustainable forest management options and policies at national, continental, and global scales (Kornatowska and Sienkiewicz, 2018). Forest economic valuation seeks to calculate the total economic worth of forest ecosystems. The entire economic value of forests is calculated by adding the use and non-use values (Gebben, 2013).

The CVM is a survey-based method for determining how much a person is ready to pay for forest resource amenities in a hypothetical market (Nicosia et al., 2014; Schutgens et al., 2019; Halkos et al., 2020). Thus, the value of

products and services is determined by the simulated market provided to respondents (Rahmatian, 2005). CVM surveys ask respondents to express their maximum WTP or minimum willingness to accept (WTA) for a hypothetical decrease in the degree of availability of forest ecosystem goods or services (Yu et al., 2018; Uyan, 2020). CVM extracts vital information regarding an individual's WTP in response to changes in the amount or quality of products or services, as well as the effect of numerous factors on WTP (Iqbal et al., 2022).

Many researchers employ contingent valuation as the method of assessing non-market forest ecosystem services by determining the WTP of the respondents. CVM has been used to determine the WTP in various areas such as coastal and marine ecosystems restoration (Mamat et al., 2013; Pham et al., 2018; Yu et al., 2018), forest and watershed restoration and conservation (Tao et al., 2012; Haltia, 2015; Lalika et al., 2017; Agundez et al., 2018; Jo et al., 2021), protected areas preservation and conservation (e.g. national parks, world heritage sites, and other tourism sites) (Samdin, 2008; Kamri, 2013; Akinyemi and Mushunje, 2017; Jin et al., 2019; Hassin et al., 2020; Kubak et al., 2020;) and biodiversity conservation (Ezebilo, 2016; Schutgens et al., 2019).

In the Philippines, few studies have been conducted to assess the economic value of non-market forest ecosystem services. For example, CVM was used to assess the WTP of local and foreign tourists for improved management and preservation of the Sagada recreational site (Abansi, 2012.); WTP for rice terraces conservation (Calderon et al., 2009); WTP for watershed conservation (Manlosa et al., 2013); WTP for improved watershed management (Carig et al., 2016) and WTP for mangroves' coastal protection (Gagarin et al., 2022). Awareness of forest-based ecosystem services is critical for understanding the unique and significant role that forests play in supporting many aspects of rural livelihood strategies and results, as well as informing optimal management regimes. Studies on the awareness and estimation of forest ecosystem services within watersheds in the Philippine context are

still limited. This study was then conducted to determine the awareness of forest ecosystem services and WTP of residents on the protection and conservation of forest ecosystems within the Abra River Basin.

Materials and Methods

Location of the Study Area

The study was conducted at the three watersheds of the Abra River Basin covering 11 municipalities (Figure 1). The Abra River Basin is the sixth largest river basin in the Philippines. The river basin is a major source of environmental, economic, and social benefits. It also hosts diverse flora and fauna species. The total forest cover of the study area is 30,105.34 ha. It is geographically located in the Northern part of the Philippines with geographic coordinates of 17°35'08.60"N and 120°32'33.50" E.

Research Design

A semi-structured questionnaire was used to elicit data from the respondents. The respondents of the study were from the 11 municipalities covered by the study area. Cochran's formula was used in determining the sample size of the study. In determining the sample size, a confidence interval of 95% and an error margin of 5% were used. Using Cochran's formula, a total of 368 household sample sizes was computed. The questionnaire was pre-tested by administering it to 25 randomly selected respondents. The questionnaire was pre-tested to ensure that all of the questions were relevant and understandable. The questionnaire has three sections: a) the Socio-demographic profile of the respondents; b) the Perception of the respondents on the direct and indirect forest ecosystem services and c) the Contingent valuation question. The respondents were briefed on the objectives and purpose of the study before administering the questionnaire.

Willingness to Pay Statistical Model

Open-ended, bidding games, payment cards, single-bounded dichotomous choice, and double-bounded dichotomous choice are the

major elicitation methods in contingent valuation surveys (Jara et al., 2021). Continuous or open-ended questions are the simplest; respondents are asked a direct question about how much they are willing to pay for a good or

service. Discrete, dichotomous choice or referendum questions ask a respondent whether they are willing to pay or not. In the dichotomous choice method, the respondents

Figure 1. Location of the Study Area

can respond yes or no. If yes, the respondent will then be asked how much they would be willing to pay based on a specified amount. The dichotomous choice is a popular method of elicitation for CVM practitioners because of its simplicity (Carig et al., 2016; Jara et al., 2022). The bidding game method asks respondents if they are willing to pay a specific amount or not. The sums are raised (or reduced) depending on whether or not the respondent is willing to pay the previously proposed amount. It stops when the iterations have reached a point estimate of WTP (Jara et al., 2022). In this study, the WTP by the respondents was obtained using the payment card method. Adopted from the study of Idris et al. (2021), the following steps were undertaken to elicit information on the WTP of the respondent: (1) Establish the hypothetical market, (2) Getting an offer of the WTP value, (3) Estimate the average value of WTP and (4) Estimate the WTP.

WTP Probability

The binary logistic regression model best estimates the probability that an individual will pay a given amount because they respond with only a ‘yes’ or ‘no’ answer (Nicosia et al., 2014; Yu et al., 2018). The logistic regression model can be expressed as:

$$P(\text{Willingness} = 1|x) = \frac{\exp(x, \beta)}{1 + \exp(x, \beta)} \quad (1)$$

where

P = probability of willingness by respondents

x = explanatory variables (age, gender, marital status, duration of residence, educational level, family size, income, occupation, and amount)

Estimation of Mean Willingness to Pay (MWTP)

The MWTP was estimated using the following formula:

$$\text{Mean WTP} = \frac{1}{\beta_1} \cdot \ln(1 + \exp(\beta_0)) \quad (2)$$

where

β_1 = bid amount coefficient

β_0 = grand constant, the sum of the estimated constant plus the product of the other explanatory variables multiplied by their average value.

Results

Socio-Demographic Profile of the Respondents

The socio-demographic profile of the respondents is presented in Table 1. In this study, a total of 368 respondents were surveyed and interviewed. The age ranges from 20 to 80 years old. 24.18% of the respondents are within

the 41-50 age bracket while 23.10% are within the 51-60 age bracket. The average age of the respondents is 44.23 years old. In terms of ethnicity, 52.45% of the respondents belong to different ethnic tribes (*Adasen, Banao, Binongan, Gubang, Inlaud, Mabaka, Maeng, Masadiit, Muyadan*), while 47.55% belong to non-indigenous people group (Ilokano, Ilongo, Tagalog, and Visayas). More than half of the respondents are female; 67.39% are married. 32.88% of the respondents are high school graduates while 27.72% are college graduates. The average duration of residence of the respondents is 36.52 years. The longest duration of residence is 80 years. 27.17% of the respondents have resided in the area for more than 50 years while 11.41% resided in the area for less than 10 years. Most of the respondents are Roman Catholic. Regarding family size, 59.24% of the respondents have a family size of 4-6. Almost all of the respondents have a monthly income of less than 10,000.00 pesos. The respondents have varied occupations. One-third of the respondents are farmers, while the rest are barangay officials, housekeepers, vendors, government employees, tricycle drivers, church ministers, and some are retired government officials.

Table 1. Socio-Demographic profile of the Respondents (n=368)

Variable	Response	Frequency	%
Age	20-30	82	22.28
	31-40	61	16.58
	41-50	89	24.18
	51-60	85	23.10
	61 and over	51	13.86
Gender	Male	216	58.70
	Female	152	41.30
Marital Status	Single	83	22.55
	Married	248	67.39
	Widow	28	7.61
	Others	9	2.45
Religious Sect	Roman Catholic	284	77.17
	Jehovah's Witnesses	11	2.99
	Iglesia ni Cristo	13	3.53
	Protestant	17	4.62
	Evangelical	1	0.27
	Islam	0	0.00

	Others	42	11.41
Duration of Residence	0-10	42	11.41
	11-20	48	13.04
	21-30	57	15.49
	31-40	50	13.59
	41-50	71	19.29
	51 and above	100	27.17
Educational Level	Elementary	46	12.50
	HS	121	32.88
	SH	9	2.45
	College Graduate	102	27.72
	College Undergraduate	89	24.18
	Graduate Studies	1	0.27
Family Size	1-3	80	21.74
	4-6	218	59.24
	7-9	44	11.96
	10 and above	26	7.07
Monthly Income	10,000 and below	335	91.03
	10,000 - 15,000	17	4.62
	15,000-20,000	5	1.36
	20,000-25,000	5	1.36
	25,000 and above	6	1.63
Indigenous People Group	Indigenous People (IP)	193	52.45
	Non-IP	175	47.55

Awareness of Forest Ecosystem Services

The awareness of the respondents on forest ecosystem services is shown in Table 2. The mean of each service was calculated based on the responses and the grand mean of the four services was also computed. The computed mean for regulating, cultural, provisioning, and

supporting services is 3.89, 3.93, 4.47, and 3.97, respectively. The grand mean is 4.07 with a descriptive equivalent of ‘aware’. The results show that the level of awareness of the respondents on the regulating, cultural, and supporting services is “aware” while “very much aware” of provisioning services.

Table 2. Awareness of Respondents on Forest Ecosystem Services

Forest Ecosystem Services	Mean	DE
A. Forest Regulating Services		
Water Purification and Regulation	3.94	Aware
Regulation of Climate and Global Warming	3.90	Aware
Pollination	3.77	Aware
Minimize pests and diseases	3.82	Aware
Air Purification	3.93	Aware
Control soil erosion	4.01	Aware
Mean for Forest Regulating Services	3.89	Aware
B. Cultural Services		
Educational	4.01	Aware
Aesthetic	3.87	Aware

Cultural Heritage Values and Identity	3.85	Aware
Recreation	3.94	Aware
Tourism	4.05	Aware
Spiritual Experiences	3.89	Aware
Mean for Forest Cultural Services	3.93	Aware
C. Provisioning Services		
Food (e.g. <i>diro</i> , <i>anibong</i> , <i>pako</i> , wildlife, wild fruits, mushroom)	4.57	Very Aware
Medicine	4.48	Very Aware
Timber, Fuelwood/Firewood	4.44	Very Aware
Clean Water	4.50	Very Aware
Rattan and bamboo as raw material for weaving	4.38	Very Aware
Mean for Forest Provisioning Services	4.47	Very Aware
D. Supporting Services		
Provision of shelter and habitats for plant and animal species	4.07	Aware
Water and Nutrient Cycling	3.96	Aware
Soil Formation	3.89	Aware
Mean for Forest Supporting Services	3.97	Aware
Grand Mean	4.07	Aware

Descriptive Equivalent: 1.00 -1.80-Not Aware at all, 1.81 – 2.60-Not Aware, 2.61 – 3.40-Somewhat Aware, 3.42-4.20-Aware, 4.21-5.0- Very Aware

Mean Willingness to Pay Estimation

Originally, 85.6% of the respondents voted yes to the WTP question. For those who voted “yes”, a follow-up question was asked about their certainty to pay with a scale of 1-5 (1 being not certain at all while 5 being certain). Those who voted yes but voted 1 and 2 on the certainty of payment were treated as a “no” response. This

technique was also done by Carig et al. (2016) in their study to those respondents who voted “yes” but also voted “not sure” and “completely not sure”. In this study, 27 (8.57%) “yes” responses were converted as a “no” response. As shown in Table 3, the final number of “yes” votes is 288 (78.26%) while 80 (21.74%) for “no” responses.

Table 3. Original and Adjusted Responses to the WTP Question

Willingness to Pay	Original Responses		Adjusted Responses	
	f	%	f	%
Yes	315	85.6	288	78.26
No	53	14.4	80	21.74
Total	368	100	368	100

Table 4 shows the regression results. Nine independent variables (age, gender, marital status, duration of residence, educational level, family size, income, occupation, and amount) were used as determinants of WTP in this study. The regression results showed that only two (marital status and amount) of the determinants

were significant. Three of the nine variables (gender, family size, and monthly income) showed a negative relationship with WTP, while six variables showed a positive relationship (age, marital status, duration of residence, educational level, amount, occupation) with WTP.

Table 4. Determinants of the WTP for Forest Protection and Conservation

Variables	Coefficient	p value
Age	0.003	0.873 ^{ns}
Gender	-0.149	0.693 ^{ns}
Marital Status	0.830	0.043*
Duration of Residence	0.006	0.662 ^{ns}
Educational Level	0.027	0.840 ^{ns}
Family Size	-0.013	0.957 ^{ns}
Monthly Income	-0.155	0.562 ^{ns}
Amount	0.246	0.000**
Occupation	0.007	0.963 ^{ns}
Constant	-1.979	0.073

Discussion

The respondents of this study are knowledgeable about the different forest ecosystem services, especially provisioning services. It is not surprising that the provisioning services had the highest mean because provisioning services are the direct and tangible benefits enjoyed by the respondents. Aside from food, the respondents also mentioned fuelwood, timber, and bamboo. Timber taken from the forest is mainly used for house construction. In addition, herbal plants are also taken from the forest and used as medicine. The very high awareness of respondents on the provisioning services of the forest ecosystem is attributed to the fact that the respondents are directly utilizing these goods and services in their daily lives for subsistence. This corroborates the study of Ahammad et al. (2019) in Bangladesh. In their study, they reported that provisioning services are more crucial for rural communities' subsistence needs than financial gains. The result of this study is also in agreement with the study of Quevedo et al. (2019) on the perception of local communities on ecosystem services provided by mangroves. The result of their study showed that respondents are extremely aware of the provisioning services of mangroves such as the source of fish. The result of the study of Gouwakinnou et al. (2019) also showed that respondents in their study identified provisioning services of forest ecosystems as the most important. In contrast, the study of Dehghani Pour et al. (2023) revealed that cultural services of forest ecosystems are the most important services identified by their

respondents. Incorporating ecosystem services into decision-making processes has garnered significant interest from the scientific community recently, as these methods consider the relevance of these services for human well-being (Quevedo et al., 2019). Determining appropriate management strategies for a multifunctional forest ecosystem requires an understanding of the state and patterns of ecosystem services in a changing environment. Local communities' perspectives on ecosystem services are vital, particularly for evaluating the sociocultural aspect of these services and guaranteeing that behavior complies with management directives and policies (Ahammad et al., 2019).

The estimated MWTP is 5.13 Philippine pesos per household per month (PhP 61.57/household/Year). Considering the total number of households in the study area which is 11,707, the aggregated MWTP is PhP 720,744.17/year. The estimated WTP is low as compared to other studies conducted in other developing countries such as Nepal (3.89 USD/hh/mo) and Ethiopia (0.64-0.75 USD/hh/mo) (Lamichhane, 2019; Getachew, 2018). The very low WTP does not mean that the local communities do not value the forests but have more pressing needs of money for education and food requirements. Most of the respondents are willing to pay a certain amount for the protection and conservation of their forests. This implies that they value their forest ecosystems and are willing to contribute a substantial amount of their monthly income for the protection and conservation of their forests.

The respondents' estimated mean WTP can be used to determine a potential cash stream for forest ecosystem protection and conservation.

The variables with significant influence on the WTP of respondents are marital status and bid amount. The bid amount usually has a negative relationship with WTP as reported in most studies. A negative coefficient indicates that a higher bid amount correlates with a lower likelihood of the responder agreeing to pay the bid amount for forest protection and conservation. For instance, the studies of Nicosia et al. (2014), Carig et al. (2016), Pham et al. (2018), Getachew (2018), Gagarin et al. (2022) reported a negative but significant correlation of bid amount to WTP. In this study, however, the variable "amount" showed a positive and significant relationship with WTP. This means that as the bid amount increases, the higher the chance of the respondent agreeing to pay the amount. This may imply that the respondents deeply care about their forest ecosystem and that they are willing to pay a higher amount for the protection and conservation of the forest. Another significant variable is marital status. This means that married couples are more willing to pay than single and widows. This finding conforms with the study of Carig et al. (2016) where marital status is an important factor.

The main reason for the WTP is because they want the forest to be conserved to sustain forest ecosystem services. The second most cited reason is because they want future generations to enjoy the services provided by the forests. On the other hand, the main reason for not willing to pay is simply, they don't have enough money.

Conclusion

This study was conducted to determine the awareness of residents about forest ecosystem services and their WTP for forest protection and conservation. The result of this study showed that the respondents are aware of the regulating, supporting, and cultural services of the forest. For provisioning services, the respondents are very aware. The estimated MWTP (PhP

5.13/month/household) is very low as compared to other studies conducted in the Philippines. The result of this study revealed the communities' awareness and their willingness to contribute part of their monthly income to financing forest protection and conservation initiatives. The findings of this study could be used as an initial basis for crafting a policy on collecting Payment for Ecosystem Services (PES). However, if PES is to be institutionalized, public consultations should be conducted before bid amounts are established, as the predicted MWTP is based on a hypothetical situation. Furthermore, the same study might be carried out in the study area's neighboring watersheds.

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Conflict of interests

The authors declare that there are no competing interests to any authors.

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